

ENERGY FORECAST FOR HETEROGENEOUS WIRELESS SENSOR NETWORKS USING CLUSTERING TREE TOPOLOGY SCHEME

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Abstract:

A Clustering-tree Topology control algorithm based on Energy Forecast (CTEF) introduced for Heterogeneous Wireless Sensor Network (HWSN) to solve the problems of energy consumption and to ensure the network load balancing. In HWSN, forecasting the energy consumption per round in the network lifetime and the actual lifespan of network is difficult than homogeneous wireless sensor network. CTEF algorithm is proposed for solving this problem. A CTEF is proposed for ensuring the network load balancing and saving energy by considering the link quality and packet loss rate. Energy consumption can be predicted more accurately in each round by considering the network lifetime. The difference between the ideal and actual average residual energy can be calculated using central limit theorem and normal distribution mechanism. The best nodes are selected as per the cluster-head cost function including the energy, link quality, packet loss rate and their distance. If the distance among cluster heads is short, more nodes will be judged to join to the cluster, which will consume more energy. Several non-cluster heads in each cluster are chosen as per the relay nodes for transmitting data through multi-hop communication in order to decrease the load of each cluster-head and prolong the lifetime of the network. CTEF has longer network lifetime and receives more data packets at base station. The network lifetime of CTEF is higher than other three algorithm because more nodes deployed to increase the total energy of the network. It also brings a burden to the cluster heads during their communications which will consume more energy. The network throughput is to be increased by increasing energy heterogeneity and parameter value.

Key Words: HWSN, Topology, Multi-Hop Communication, Base Station & Energy Heterogeneity

1. Introduction:

HETEROGENEOUS wireless sensor network (HWSN) is a wireless ad hoc network which is consisted of a large number of different types of sensor nodes. Unlike homogeneous WSN, nodes are randomly deployed in the monitored area, which are equipped with extremely different energy. Heterogeneity can sharply increase the average delivery rate and the network lifetime if nodes are deployed as an effective network [1]. Therefore, HWSN has more realistic and broader applications than homogeneous WSN. However, due to their irreducibility of nodes and the limitations [2], one of the major challenges is how to effectively use the energy and extend the network lifetime in such a complex heterogeneous network. Topology control is one of the most important techniques used for reducing energy consumption and maintaining network connectivity [1]. For topology control, there are many reactive and proactive techniques in WSN. Recently, clustering technology has already been proven that it has certain advantages in energy efficiency and scalability, e.g., low energy adaptive clustering hierarchy (LEACH) [8]. Specially, stable election protocol (SEP) [9] and distributed energy efficient clustering (DEEC) [10] are proposed for heterogeneous network. But the previously proposed algorithms still have issues as follows: 1) Lacking consideration of more complicated scenarios, e.g., the link quality and packet loss rate; 2) Lacking consideration of the distance among the clusters during the cluster-head selection; 3) Lacking consideration of the overload problem of cluster-head. In many scenarios, we have to face such a complicated real networks which suffer from the resource limitations that the traditional method cannot be suitable for them. Thus, we focus on how to design an energy-efficient algorithm or protocol for HWSN to maximize the network lifetime while considering the link quality, packet loss rate and any other complex scenarios. A clustering-tree topology control algorithm based on energy forecast (CTEF) is introduced for HWSN in order to solve the problem how to save energy and ensure the network load balancing. In HWSN, forecasting the energy consumption per round during the network lifetime and the actual lifespan of network is much more difficult than homogeneous WSN. We propose CTEF algorithm for solving this problem in an efficient way in terms of the estimated difference between the ideal average residual energy and the actual average residual energy to obtain the average energy of network at the next round. The cluster heads are selected depending on the synthesized cost function and their distance, while the clusters are formed by combining with the factors of the energy, distance and link quality. Moreover, to reduce the burden of the cluster-head, several non-cluster head nodes in each cluster are chosen as the relay nodes for transmitting data through multi-hop communication. The performance of CTEF is evaluated and found better than other typical protocols and algorithms via simulation.

2. Related Work:

Clustering scheme is one of the most typical ways for topology control in WSN. Most of cluster-based algorithms always adopt data fusion scheme and pursue clustering objectives [6] such as load balancing, fault-tolerance, increasing connectivity, reducing time delay, maximizing network longevity, etc.. In the past few years, LEACH [8] and its improved algorithms were represented as one of the most well-known distributed cluster-based topology control algorithm with scalability and energy conservation in WSN. However, it may not be suitable for heterogeneity because of its ideal network model [11]. Recently; quite a lot of energy-oriented algorithms for HWSN are proposed. For instance, energy efficient heterogeneous clustered (EEHC) algorithm is proposed based on the three-level network model in [7], which is composed of supernodes, advanced nodes and ordinary nodes. EEHC utilizes the best number of clusters calculation method proposed from LEACH, and it selects cluster heads by residual energy of nodes and weighted probability mechanism. Then the non-cluster head nodes are attracted by the cluster heads to form clusters and the network begins to transmit data. Zhou et al. [12] propose a clustering protocol energy dissipation forecast and clustering management (EDFCM) based on the two-level network composed of super nodes and ordinary nodes. Similar to EEHC, the method for calculating the best number of clusters from LEACH is also cited by EDFCM. Furthermore, a mathematical model of energy consumption is proposed to compute the weighted probability of node for selecting cluster head by residual energy and the approximate average energy consumption at the next round of network lifetime. However, the approximate average energy consumption at the next round of network is likely to cause deviation in practice because it is an ideal energy value. An efficient and dynamic clustering scheme (EDCS) is proposed for multi-level heterogeneous wireless sensor networks in [11]. EDCS determines the probability of node to be a cluster-head through estimating the average residual energy of the network in the next round by average energy consumption forecast according to ideal state and the reference value of historical energy consumption, simultaneously. Analogous universal gravitation is introduced to ensure non-cluster head nodes join cluster in terms of gravitation during cluster formation. Kuila et al [13] propose a load balancing method based on genetic algorithms. Sensor nodes are regarded as the chromosome number and the chromosomes are assigned to the corresponding gateway. Also, the standard deviation of load is utilized to determine whether the node is with load balancing. Dabirmoghaddam et al. [14] propose an optimal uniform clustering (OUC) for prolonging the network lifetime and strengthening the network scalability. In OUC, the general problem of optimal clustering with arbitrary cluster-head selection is demonstrated to be NP-hard. Sensor nodes form clusters in a distributed manner using a probabilistic cluster head selection. The main difference between what we mentioned in above and our solution described in the following lies in network model. We use more general network model with multi-level heterogeneous features, which means we need to further take into account more complicated and actual factors and situations. As a clustering-tree topology control scheme, CTEF has advantages both from the clustering and tree algorithms. Energy consumption can be predicted more accurately in each round during the network lifetime, which results to be more reasonable for cluster-head selection and cluster formation. In addition, to avoid excessive energy consumption from the cluster-head, several non-cluster head nodes are chosen to be the relay node to further reduce the burden of each cluster head. That is why CTEF with multi-hop communication can have longer lifetime.

3. Heterogeneous Model for WSN:

A. Types of Heterogeneity and Impact on WSN: Unlike homogeneous WSN, there are many special features in HWSN. Generally, the common types of heterogeneity in WSN are classified as follows:

- ✓ Computational heterogeneity: Different nodes have different capabilities to store information or deal with emergent events. Some super or advanced nodes have more powerful processor and memory than any other normal nodes. With high performance hardware, these nodes which own powerful computational capabilities can provide more and more ability for data storage and complex data processing, e.g., data fusion is executed when the node receives a large number of data at the same time.
- ✓ Link heterogeneity: With similarity to the computational heterogeneity, due to the powerful electronic devices, some nodes have more channels, higher bandwidth and longer communication distance than normal nodes. So they can provide more reliable and robust data transmission network.
- ✓ Energy heterogeneity: It is the most important and key point in these three common types of heterogeneity. Computational heterogeneity and link heterogeneity always lead to consuming more energy than nodes in homogenous network so that their lifetime will fall down quickly. Energy heterogeneity can be represented as which nodes are equipped with different times of energy virtually.

In homogeneous WSN, each node has the same computational and communication capability, initial energy, and dissipates equivalent energy per round. However, the practical WSN is always composed of multiple sensors which are given different processing capabilities and initial energy. Each node has multi-level power options such that it consumes different energy per round in the normal working time depending on its current power level. Also, the link quality and packet loss rate should be taken into account for HWSN firstly because it could easily exist in such a complicated wireless situation. In addition, the interference can happen among

nodes and clusters. Thus, the heterogeneous WSN with limitations is more suitable for research and more approximated to actual network.

B. Network Model: Assume that N sensor nodes, which are all different from each other, are dispersed uniformly in an $M \times M$ square region. Besides, it has some features as follows:

- ✓ Each node is equipped with a different initial energy which determines the value of the maximal initial energy;
- ✓ The communication cost is different between nodes, and link quality and packet loss rate are arbitrary values;
- ✓ The non-cluster heads cannot be allowed to communicate with the base station (BS) directly, only the cluster-head can send data directly to the base station;
- ✓ The fusion strategies are executed by the cluster-head to aggregate correlated data before transmitting to the base station;
- ✓ The distance between nodes is calculated by the received signal strength indicator (RSSI);
- ✓ The interference can be neglected by using CSMA/CA in MAC layer.
- ✓ The sink node is located at the center of region, and it is not restricted by energy, etc.

4. CTEF Algorithm:

Our proposed algorithm CTEF aims to find an effective way for HWSN to save energy consumption and prolong the network lifetime. We can clearly see from Fig.1 that the CTEF is mainly divided into four parts, i.e., the average energy of the network estimation, the cluster-head selection, the cluster formation and tree formation within cluster.

Figure 1: The flow chart of CTEF algorithm.

A. Cluster-Head Selection: Network load balancing is to improve the lifetime of the network, there are three factors to combine (i.e., node energy, link quality and packet loss rate) used to evaluate the cost of each node performance. The best nodes are selected as the cluster-head by cost function. The node which has more energy, higher link quality and lower packet loss rate, will be selected as the cluster-head. Compared to other nodes, these cluster heads will have more available energy, while their rate of transmitting data will be higher. The remaining nodes will collect data in the monitoring region as the member of each cluster. So the network performance will be better. Cluster heads will have high energy, and their rate of transmitting data will be higher.

$$C = \frac{1}{\beta \left(\frac{E_{res}}{E_{total}(r)} \right) + \left(p_{link} + \left(\frac{1}{p_{loss}} \right)^{\frac{(1-\beta)}{2}} \right)}$$

After the node has been selected as the cluster-head, it needs to broadcast the message to other nodes in the network and waits for response. The cluster-head can be seen at the center of the cluster region, because the communication range of nodes is always be a circle. Once each non-cluster head node receives the invitation messages from multiple cluster heads, it computes the distance $d(i, j)$ between the sender and the receiver based on the Receiver Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI).

$$F(i, j, r) = \frac{E_{res}^j p_{link}}{d(i, j)}$$

For cluster formation, a method is introduced to guide the non-cluster head nodes and to choose the most suitable cluster-head, which depends on the energy in cluster-head the link quality between the cluster-head and the non-cluster head nodes, and the distance $d(i, j)$ can also be used to determine which cluster to join for the

non-cluster head node. It means that the longer distance between the cluster-head and the non-cluster head nodes, the less possibility the non-cluster head nodes to join.

B. Tree Formation Within the Cluster: Clustering algorithm is mainly used for load balancing. If a cluster has too many members, the cluster-head will consume too much energy to communicate with the cluster members. The way to search transferring nodes from cluster members is proposed which can used to construct a tree in the cluster. It aims to reduce the energy consumption and prolong the lifetime because of sharing the load of cluster heads to balance the energy consumption in clusters.

Figure 2: Cluster area divided in two regions

After the cluster formation, a cluster-head can be seen as the circle center and L_2 is the radius to divide the cluster area into two parts, i.e., a circle and an approximate ring. It is shown in Fig.2, where L_3 is the distance from the cluster-head to the edge of cluster.

Figure 3: Division of the cluster area by the cross axis

The cluster head is regarded as the original point of cross axis. The cross axis divides the cluster area into four regions, like I, II, III and IV, which is illustrated in Fig. 3. Then in the regions (I1, I2, II1, II2, III1, III2, IV1 and IV2), the relay nodes are searched to receive the messages from others in order to transmit to the cluster-head. is a variance of the distance, which means that then lower variance of node i , the more uniform distribution around the node i . If a node has more energy and less distance variance to the cluster-head, it will be more likely to become a relay node.

5. Result Analysis:

The lifetime is the one of the most important performance criteria to verify the CTEF algorithm. The influence of network lifetime within different number of nodes and energy parameter

The parameter evaluations are

Energy: The analysis between number of nodes and energy is represented in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Energy of network

The proposed scheme incur less energy compared to the LEACH,EDCS,EDFCM algorithm.

2. Throughput: LEACH protocol is only suitable for homogeneous network, i.e., it can obtain good communication efficiency in the homogeneous environment, but cannot perform very well in the multi-level heterogeneous network. The EDFCM protocol has much longer steady stage of communication than LEACH which is the period from the beginning of network lifetime to the time when the first node dies. Similar with EDFCM, the EDCS protocol has much longer steady stage of communication, but both of them cannot use the node energy efficiently in the later communications which is also called unstable period. Compared with LEACH, EDFCM and EDCS, our proposed CTEF is better in terms of the network lifetime. Network lifetime decreases relatively slowly as compared to other algorithms. It means that CTEF uses the unstable period efficiently which is very critical, because under the real network environment, it is possible that some nodes will be dead at any time owing to unexpected events. The network throughput is to be increased by increasing energy heterogeneity parameter value.

Figure 5: Packet Reception

3. Network Lifetime: It helpful to prolong the network lifetime with these algorithms by increasing λ , where λ is set from 0.5 to 4.0 respectively. The network lifetime of CTEF is longer than other three algorithms regardless of how λ changes and the rate increases when the energy parameter λ is gradually increasing. This is because of more nodes deployed to increase the total energy of the network, it also brings a burden to the cluster heads during their communications which will consume more energy. However, by increasing λ , total network energy increases. And the increased energy is greater than the additional energy consumption, which makes more available energy and prolongs the network lifetime.

6. Conclusion:

The proposed scheme on CTEF solves the problem of energy consumption through considering the energy and link heterogeneity. The network lifetime of CTEF is higher than other three algorithm because more nodes deployed to increase the total energy of the network. It also brings a burden to the cluster heads during their communications which will consume more energy. The network throughput is to be increased by increasing energy heterogeneity parameter value.

7. References:

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